

Solubility Profile and Effects of Ph-NaCl on the Emulsifying and Foaming Properties of Sandbox (*Hura Crepitana*) Protein Concentrate and Isolate

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Abstract

This paper studied the effect of pH on protein solubility as well as effects of pH and NaCl between pH 2–10 and NaCl concentration of 0.0–1.0 M; respectively on the emulsifying and foaming properties of sandbox seed protein concentrate and isolate prepared; by soaking, cooking, fermenting, defatting, solubilizing and freeze drying analyzed using standard experimental procedures. The protein solubility of sandbox seed protein isolate was most soluble at pH10 (57.63%) and its concentrate was 64.68% at same pH, while at its isoelectric points (pH4) yielded 23.37% and 23.47% for the isolate and concentrate; respectively. The pH-emulsifying property profile of the proteins followed the trends of its pH-solubility profile and salt concentrations between 0.5 M and 1.0 M significantly ($P < 0.05$) decreased the emulsifying property. However, foaming properties of the samples yielded good volumes as salt concentration increased from 0.0 - 0.5 M NaCl, and decreased at 1.0 M NaCl concentration.

Key Words: Functional properties, pH, Protein isolate, Protein solubility, Salt concentration

INTRODUCTION

Food characteristics are measured by quality attributes and stability properties of a product and these features are expected to be directly relative and dependent on the functional properties their proteins exhibit (Xiong, 2000). It is, however, noteworthy that consequent to the global demand for proteins, new sources for protein from plants have been sought for and explored for its good functional properties, acceptable nutritional values and its prospective successes to the food industry (Akubor *et al.*, 2003). Nevertheless, the significance of utilizing plant proteins as additives depends greatly upon the favourable characteristics (emulsifying, foaming and gelling ability) that they impact on foods (Albo, 2001; Eleazar *et al.*, 2003). On the other hand, emulsifying and foaming properties vividly are the two known vital functional parameters that protein products ought to possess in the improvement of novel foods; in order to facilitate stable oil droplet formation through development of interfacial membranes (Halling, 1981), and membrane formation or barrier establishment to prevent coalescence of air bubbles (Aluko and Yada, 1995).

Compositely, several other factors also affect the functional properties of proteins of foods including thickening, water holding capacity, and fat binding (Damodaran, 1996), which further aids their ability to provide definite and required characteristics in food applications (Schmidt, 1981; Ziegler and Foegeding, 1990; McClements, 2002). According to Wang *et al.* (2011) and Zhao *et al.* (2015), proteins' functionality essentially is for emulsification, while polysaccharides improve the stability of emulsions by thickening and stabilizing properties. Furthermore, the functional properties of food proteins are distinct for a combination of specific proteins characterized by their synergistic and/or otherwise antagonistic effect on final functionality (Yuan *et al.*, 2009; Wong *et al.*, 2013). In addition, the acid-soluble proteins of some leguminous plants have very high foaming properties as compared to their alkaline-soluble proteins, resulting in a specific protein combination (Wong *et al.*, 2013). Notably, acid-aided and alkaline-aided solubilization (or pH-shift) has resourcefully accelerated the recovery of and improved the functional and

nutritious protein isolates from sources that are underexplored and crude, with potentials for utility (Chen and Jaczynski, 2007; Gehring *et al.*, 2011; Chomnawang and Yongsawatdigul, 2013; Matak *et al.*, 2015). Abdulkadir *et al.* (2013) investigations revealed the chemical composition of sandbox seed (*Hura crepitans*). The seed contains amongst other proximate composition contains 37.62% protein content. Sandbox seed is a promising seed for future food and feed and can be regarded as a neglected and underutilized food crop (NUFC). It is however noteworthy that most NUFCs are part of a vast range of biodiversified portfolio of crops neglected, that have vital roles to play in food and nutrition security (Padulosi *et al.*, 2002; Frison *et al.*, 2006; Hawtin *et al.*, 2007; Erlund *et al.*, 2008; Katoch, 2013; Sridhar and Niveditha, 2014). Considering the high level of protein (37.62%) in sandbox seed, and in order to evaluate its potentiality in food product formulation, processing the whole flour to protein-rich products such as defatted flour, protein concentrate and isolate could enhance its utilization as a protein supplement. Despite the previous efforts of Fowomola and Akindahunsi (2008), Olatidoye *et al.* (2010), Oyeleke *et al.* (2012), Gbadamosi and Osungbade (2017) and Ige *et al.* (2019), there is a paucity of information regarding the effect of different pH and salt concentration on the functional properties of sandbox seed flours and proteins. Thus, this study expanded the utilization of the seeds by preparing defatted flour, protein concentrate and isolate, investigated and provided information on the effect of pH-NaCl of sandbox seed flours and proteins, and protein solubility.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection

Dried dispersed sandbox (*Hura crepitans*) seeds and pods were collected from sandbox trees at Parks and Gardens in Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria. The pods were further broken to collect more seeds, moistened with tap water together with the collected dispersed seed in order to soften the shell and were decorticated manually, air dried and stored in tight moisture-free polythene bags at -10°C for further use. All chemicals used were of analytical grades and were acquired from Fisher Scientific (Oakville, ON, Canada) and Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).

Preparation of defatted flours, protein concentrate and isolate

The preparation of whole and fermented sandbox flour samples was as described and adapted from Ige *et al.* (2019) to obtain homogenous full-fat flours of untreated sandbox flour (USF), cooked, fermented sandbox flour (CFS), and soaked fermented sandbox flour (SFS). The defatted flours were prepared as described by Sathe (1994) as modified by Gbadamosi *et al.* (2012) from untreated sandbox flour (DUS), defatted cooked, fermented sandbox flour (DCF), and defatted soaked fermented sandbox flour (DSF) to obtain defatted untreated sandbox flour (DUS), defatted cooked, fermented sandbox flour (DCF) and defatted soaked fermented sandbox flour (DSF); respectively. The full-fat flour was defatted using cold (4°C) acetone (flour to solvent ratio 1:5 w/v) with constant stirring for 4 h with a magnetic stirrer (Compact Magnetic Stirrer, United Kingdom). The defatted flour was placed inside a fume cupboard for 6 h to dry and to remove any trace of residual acetone. The flakes were then ground again and sieved (Endecotts sieve, United Kingdom) through a sieve size mesh of 150 µm to obtain the fine powder, packed in plastic tubes and stored at -10°C. Sandbox protein concentrate (SPC) was prepared as described by Cheftel *et al.* (1985) from defatted soaked fermented sandbox flour (DSF). The method described by Chavan *et al.* (2001) was adopted to prepare sandbox protein isolate (SPI) from defatted soaked fermented sandbox flour (DSF).

Protein solubility

The effect of pH on protein solubility of sandbox seed protein concentrate and the isolate was determined by a method described by Gbadamosi *et al.* (2012) as modified by Fasuan *et al.* (2018).

Effect of pH and NaCl concentration on emulsifying and foaming properties

The method described by Gbadamosi *et al.* (2012) was used to investigate the effect of pH and salt concentration on emulsifying properties of the sandbox protein concentrate and isolate, while the effect of pH and salt concentration on foaming properties also were determined by a modification of the method

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described by Chavan *et al.* (2001). Approximately 2 g of protein sample was dispersed in 100ml of distilled water at different NaCl concentration levels (0.0, 0.5 and 1.0M) and the pH of the protein solution was gradually adjusted using either 1N HCl or 1N NaOH in separate tubes between pH 2-10. The solution was then homogenized for 2 min using blender set (SN2200 O'Qlink, Beijing, China) at high speed, thereafter emptied into a 250ml measuring cylinder. Hence, the percentage ratio of the volume increase to that of the original volume of protein solution in the measuring cylinder was calculated and expressed as foaming capacity or whip ability. Foaming stability was expressed as a percentage of the volume of foam remaining in the measuring cylinder to that of the original volume after 30 min of the quiescent period.

$$\text{Foaming capacity (\%)} = \frac{(\text{volume after whipping} - \text{volume before whipping})\text{ml}}{(\text{volume before whipping})\text{ml}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Foaming stability (\%)} = \frac{(\text{volume after whipping} - \text{volume after standing})\text{ml}}{(\text{volume after whipping} - \text{volume before whipping})\text{ml}} \times 100$$

Statistical analysis

Data collected from all experiments were in triplicate, and analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out using SPSS Statistics 20.0 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Differences between the treatment means were separated using Duncan's multiple range test.

RESULTS

The protein solubility of sandbox seed protein concentrate and isolate were observed to be least (23.47% and 23.37%, respectively) at pH 4 while they exhibited the highest solubility at pH 10 (64.68% and 57.63%, respectively) shown in Figure 1. Kudre *et al.* (2013) reported that the occurrence of minimum solubility near the isoelectric point (*pI*) was due primarily to net charges of proteins being neutral as pH approached *pI*, and which increases as pH moves away from the isoelectric point, as a result of electrostatic repulsive forces between the positively charged proteins keeping them apart and increase protein-solvent interactions. Protein solubility of SPI compared favorably with peanut protein isolate (60.5%) (Yu *et al.*, 2007) and the results suggest that sandbox seed proteins could readily be solubilized using alkaline media.

The effects of pH and NaCl concentrations on the emulsifying activity index (EAI) and emulsion stability index (ESI) of the samples are presented in Figures 2 and 3. At 0.0M NaCl concentration, the lowest EAI and ESI for samples DUS (5.31m²/g and 62.13%), DSF (1.99m²/g and 8.62%), SPC (6.60m²/g and 28.35%) and SPI (6.01m²/g and 62.48%) were observed around their isoelectric region (pH 4) with significant difference ($P < 0.05$), while the highest EAI and ESI of DUS (33.88m²/g and 97.95%), DSF (43.19m²/g and 34.73%), SPC (42.76m²/g and 128.99%) and SPI (35.85m²/g and 180.49%) occurred at pH 10. The trends also indicated that EAI was pH-dependent and alkaline pH values were more efficient in improving the emulsion capacity than acidic pH values. According to Wang *et al.* (2009), pH had vital effects on EAI since soluble proteins emulsifying activity depends upon the hydrophilic-lipophilic balance, which in turn is affected by pH. The emulsion stability for the samples was as well similar to the report of Ogunwolu *et al.* (2009) that the pH-emulsifying property profile of various proteins exhibits the trends of its pH-solubility profile. As salt concentration increases (to 0.5 M and 1.0M), the EAI and ESI of studied samples decreased compared to its attributes at 0.0M salt concentration. The trends of EAI increase and decrease with the addition of NaCl observed in this study were similar to the observations of Chavan *et al.* (2001) and Osman *et al.* (2005) where it was observed that the hydrodynamics of protein molecules in food system was greatly influenced by prevalent ionic strength and concentration.

The results of the effect of pH and salt concentrations on foaming capacity (FC) and foam stability (FS) are presented in Figures 4 and 5. At 0.0M NaCl concentration, the lowest FC and FS of DUS (16.84% and 13.68%), DSF (30.00% and 20.00%), SPC (9.09% and 4.55%), and SPI (12.00% and 0.00%) were observed at pH 4, similar to the pH at which they exhibited their lowest solubility and emulsifying properties. The highest FC and FS were also exhibited at pH 10 as observed in DUS (41.05% and 38.95%), DSF (105.83% and 92.50%), SPC (23.00% and 17.00%), and SPI (90.00% and 31.00%). The FC and FS of the samples were observed to increase with the increase in salt concentration from 0.0M to 0.5M NaCl, and decreased as salt concentration increased to 1.0M, except at pH 2 to 10 for SPC where it was observed that FC and FS

increased with increase in salt concentrations. This investigation was consistent with the report on defatted brebra and soybean flour, where FC increases with an increase in the concentration of NaCl and decreases with a further increase in NaCl concentration (Andualem and Gessesse, 2013). According to Aremu *et al.* (2008), foaming capacity was observed to be concentration-dependent, and at high concentrations of different salt, solutions were found to reduce foaming in ground bean and bambara groundnuts. The low foam property observed at high salt concentrations was also due to the colloidal suspension during foam formation, resulting in retarded partial denaturation of the surface polypeptides of proteins that are essential for protein-protein interaction. The increase and decrease in FS with an increase in salt concentration may as well be attributed to the salting in and salting out the effect of NaCl (Mohamed Ahmed *et al.*, 2012). The improved foaming capacity of samples in the presence of NaCl may subsequently improve their functionalities to be a useful additive for the production of cakes and drinks.

CONCLUSION

The solubility of sandbox seed proteins is an indicator that it is an ideal raw material for successful utilization in various food products. Therefore, defatted sandbox seed flours, protein concentrate and isolate can be consumed/used as food and food ingredients such as emulsifying and foaming agents, especially in ice-cream and whipped toppings. However, further researches are required to expand the *in vivo* characteristics of its functional properties using animal experiments and/or different standardized approaches.

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FIGURE LEGEND

Figure 1: Effect of pH on protein solubility of sandbox seed proteins

Figure 2: Emulsifying activity index (m^2g^{-1}) of DUS, DSF, SPC and SPI at (a) 0.0 M, (b) 0.5 M and (c) 1.0 M NaCl concentration as a function of pH

Figure 3: Emulsion stability (%) of DUS, DSF, SPC and SPI at (a) 0.0 M, (b) 0.5 M and (c) 1.0 M NaCl concentration as a function of pH

Figure 4: Foam capacity (%) of DUS, DSF, SPC and SPI at (a) 0.0 M, (b) 0.5 M and (c) 1.0 M NaCl concentration as a function of pH

Figure 5: Foam stability (%) of DUS, DSF, SPC and SPI at (a) 0.0 M, (b) 0.5 M and (c) 1.0 M NaCl concentration as a function of pH

Values reported are means \pm standard deviation of triplicate determinations. Mean values with different superscript within the same row are significantly ($P < 0.05$) different. **DUS:** Defatted untreated sandbox flour; **DSF:** Defatted soaked fermented sandbox flour; **SPC:** Sandbox Protein Concentrate; **SPI:** Sandbox Protein Isolate

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Figure 1

(a)

(b)

(c)

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Figure 2

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 3

(a)

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(b)

(c)

Figure 4

(a)

(b)

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(c)

Figure 5